

Extraction behaviour of gold(III) from bromide media using some neutral organophosphine extractants

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Organophosphine compounds form strong complexes with Au^{III}. This behaviour has been studied as a function of different variables, such as hydrobromic acid concentration, reagent concentration and effect of temperature with Cyanex-921, 923, 925 and 471X in toluene from bromide media. The extraction is observed with Cyanex-921, 923 and 925 in toluene from 4.0 to 6.0 M HBr media, while with Cyanex-471X in toluene from 1.0 to 4.0 M HBr media. The extraction reaction with Cyanex 471X is endothermic, while that with Cyanex-921, 923 and 925 is exothermic in nature. The extraction phenomenon seems to depend upon the donor atom present in the extractant. The methods developed are successfully applied for analysis of gold in real samples.

Various solvent extraction methods for gold have been reported¹. Sastre *et al.*² used LIX 79 while Catterel *et al.*³ LIX 471X from cyanide and chloride media respectively, requiring multistep stripping and recovery is incomplete. Akita and Takeluh⁴ used non-ionic surfactant polyoxyethylene and non-phenyl ester but were found to co-extract iron. Organophosphorous extractants are potential and suitable for solvent in pulp (SIP) system⁵. Selectivity of Aliquat 336⁶ for Au^{III} over Cu and Fe is very high but over Ni and Zn is very low. Extraction with tributyl phosphate (TBP)⁷ and dibutyl butyl phosphonate (DBBP) is quantitative but not with dibutylcarbitol (DBC) and methyl isobutyl ketone (MIBK). The tertiary amine Alamine 304⁸ is less selective for quantitative extraction of Au^{III} but Cyanex-471X is selective⁹. The influence of acid chloride concentration on gold extraction was analyzed by applying the specific interaction theory¹⁰ (SIT). Extraction of Au^{III} from chloride media with Cyanex-923 and Cyanex-925 and its separation from Pt^{IV}, Pd^{III} and Ir^{III} has also been studied^{11,12}.

The present study deals with extraction of Au^{III} from different Cyanex extractants, Cyanex-921, 923, 925 and 471X in toluene from bromide media.

Results and Discussion

Effect of hydrobromic acid concentration : The extraction study of Au^{III} was carried out in the range of 0.1–8.0 M HBr with Cyanex-921, 923, 925 and 471X in toluene. The quantitative extraction was observed from 4.0 to 6.0 M HBr with Cyanex-921, 923 and 925, and from 1.0 to 4.0 M HBr

with Cyanex-471X. Decrease in the extraction of Au^{III} at higher acid concentration seems to be due to competition between metal ion and HBr to associate with the reagent, which is similar to the reported metal-extractant systems¹¹ like amine alamine-304 and Cyanex-923 with Au^{III} extraction from HCl media. The order found was Cyanex-921 < 923 < 925 << 471X.

Reagent concentration dependence : Extraction was found to be quantitative with minimum of 0.8×10^{-1} , 1.0×10^{-1} , 1.2×10^{-1} and 1.6×10^{-1} M for Cyanex-921, 923, 925 and 471X in toluene, respectively. The nature of extracted species was ascertained from the linear plots of log *D* vs log [R] from HBr media. The slope 1.5 observed with Cyanex-471 indicates that the stoichiometric ratio is in between 1 : 1 and 1 : 2, similar to the earlier report⁹. While slope of ≈ 2 with other extractants Cyanex-921, 923 and 925 is similar to earlier report¹².

Effect of equilibrium time : The influence of equilibrium period was studied for 1 to 20 min. The extraction equilibrium of Au^{III} was achieved with 1 min for the extractants having O donor atom (Cyanex-921, 923 and 925) while 4 min for the extraction with S containing Cyanex-471X. However, with further increase in shaking time, there was no adverse effect in the percentage extraction upto 20 min in all the cases.

Influence of diluents : It was found that Cyanex-471X favours quantitative extraction only with aromatic diluents (toluene, xylene, benzene, *n*-hexane, cyclohexane), while other three extractants favour quantitative extraction in aro-

matic as well as aliphatic diluents (toluene, xylene, benzene, *n*-hexane, cyclohexane, chloroform and carbon tetrachloride).

Influence of diverse ions on percentage extraction of Au^{III} : Au^{III} was extracted in presence of a large number of foreign ions with these extractants in toluene (Table 1) by adjusting the tolerance limit, the foreign ions causing interference of $\pm 2\%$ on extraction. The transition metal ions, alkali and alkaline earth metal ions are tolerated for $> 1 : 8$ to $< 1 : 20$ ratio while other noble metal ions for $< 1 : 5$ ratio.

Table 1. Effect of diverse ions on extraction of Au^{III} (10 μ g) from bromide media

Sl. no.	Metal ions	Tolerance limit (ratio of Au ^{III} : foreign ion)			
		Cyanex-921	Cyanex-923	Cyanex-925	Cyanex-471X
1.	Na ^I , K ^I , Cs ^I , Rb ^I , Mg ^{II} , Ca ^{II} , Ba ^{II} , Sr ^{II}	1 : 20	1 : 20	1 : 20	1 : 20
2.	V ^V , Mn ^{II} , Co ^{II} , Cu ^{II} , Ni ^{II} , Cd ^{II}	1 : 10	1 : 13	1 : 13	1 : 18
3.	Cr ^{II} , Fe ^{III} , Zn ^{II} , Al ^{III} , Bi ^{III} , Pb ^{II}	1 : 8	1 : 10	1 : 10	1 : 12
4.	Rh ^{III} , Ir ^{II}	1 : 2	1 : 3	1 : 3	1 : 5
5.	Pt ^{II}	1 : 0	1 : 0	1 : 0	1 : 2
6.	Pd ^{II} , Os ^{VIII} , Ag ^I	1 : 0	1 : 0	1 : 0	1 : 0
7.	Cl ⁻ , I ⁻ , SO ₃ ²⁻ , S ²⁻ , PO ₄ ³⁻ , citrate, oxalate	1 : 20	1 : 20	1 : 20	1 : 20

Effect of temperature : The effect of temperature on the extraction of Au^{III} was also studied in the range 273–343 K in HBr media with these extractants. The plots of $\log D$ vs $1/T \times 1000$ (K) were linear. The ΔH (change of enthalpy) values of -41.45 , -36.09 and -29.04 kJ mol⁻¹ for Cyanex-921, 923 and 925, respectively, indicate exothermic reactions with these extractants having O as a donor atom. However, it is 25.16 kJ mol⁻¹ for Cyanex-471X, which indicates endothermic reactions with the extractant having S as a donor atom. These values are in good agreement with that reported^{9,11}.

Effect of stripping agents : The extracted Au^{III} was recovered from the metal-loaded organic phase by stripping with varying concentration of different acids HCl, HNO₃, H₂SO₄, and HClO₄ as well as bases NaOH, NH₃ and Na₂S₂O₃. The quantitative stripping was found with 3.0, 2.0 and 2.0 M perchloric acid for Au^{III} extracted with Cyanex-921, 923 and 925 (NaOH, NH₃ and Na₂S₂O₃ form emulsion with organic phase). The complete stripping from the metal-loaded with Cyanex-471X was observed with 0.10 M Na₂S₂O₃ (NaOH and NH₃ gives precipitation).

Validity of method : The proposed methods were employed for the analysis of gold in pharmaceutical samples like Goldar and Ridaur. The experimental results were found to be in good agreement with the theoretical values (Table 2).

Table 2. Analysis of Au^{III} present* in real pharmaceutical samples

Extractant	Sample	Recovery**	R.S.D.
		%	%
Cyanex-921	Goldar	99.1	0.30
	Ridaur	99.4	0.18
Cyanex-923	Goldar	98.7	0.35
	Ridaur	98.8	0.38
Cyanex-925	Goldar	98.5	0.64
	Ridaur	98.7	0.55
Cyanex-471	Goldar	99.2	0.27
	Ridaur	99.4	0.15

*Reported amount (by manufacturer) of Au^{III} in Goldar and Ridaur = 3.0 mg/ml.

**Mean of triplicate values.

Conclusion :

The extraction of Au^{III} from HBr as a HAuBr₄ is more effective¹³ than from HCl media with O containing reagents. This was expected because AuBr₃ in aqueous media is generally weaker than AuCl₃, so extraction is high due to the large size and the large aquophobic¹⁴ tendency of the AuBr₃. The concentration of Cyanex-921 required for quantitative extraction was very low (0.08 M), as compared to other reagents. This behavior may be attributed to the presence 99% of trioctyl phosphine oxide (TOPO) in the extractant Cyanex-921, whereas Cyanex-923 and 925 contain about 92.4 and 65.9% TOPO respectively¹⁵; however, Cyanex-471X, triisobutyl phosphine sulfide has S as a donor. The extraction reactions with extractants having O as a donor atom are exothermic while that with S as a donor atom are endothermic in nature. Thus Cyanex-921 seems to be the powerful extractant for extraction of Au^{III} in bromide media as compared to Cyanex-923, 925 and 471X.

Experimental

A G.B.C.-911A UV/visible spectrophotometer was used. The extractants Cyanex-921, 923, 925 and 471X (Cytex Industries Inc., Canada)¹⁶ were used as such. A stock solution of Au^{III} was prepared by dissolving AuCl₃ (Sisco) in minimum quantity of HCl and standardized¹⁷; the required concentration of this solution was prepared by further dilution with double-distilled water. Goldar (gold sodium thiomalate) a mixture of mono- and disodium salt of gold (composition : C₄H₄AuNaO₄S and C₄H₃AuNa₂O₄S) was

procured from Cadila Healthcare India Ltd., and Ridaura (Auranofin) [(2,3,4,6-tetra-*O*-acetyl-1-thio- β -D-glucopyranosato)(triethylphosphine)gold], (composition : C₂₀H₃₄AuO₉PS) was procured from Smithkline Beecham India Ltd. All other chemicals used were of A.R. grade. Goldar and Ridaura are both freely soluble in water. Their solutions were made by treating with HCl (1ml) and 30% H₂O₂ (0.5 ml). The excess of H₂O₂ was decomposed by heating. The solution was then cooled and used for spectrophotometric determination of gold.

Extraction procedure : An aqueous phase (10 ml) having 100 μ g of Au^{III} in required amount of HBr was equilibrated with equal volume of the extractant (Cyanex-921/923/925/471X) in toluene. All distribution equilibria studies were carried out at 25 \pm 1.0°. The metal ion from organic phase was stripped with varying strengths of different stripping agents and the amount of Au^{III} present in aqueous phase was determined spectrophotometrically by rhodamine B¹⁸ at 555 nm.

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